

PCA, SPCA & Krylov-based PCA for Image and Video Processing

¹ Amanda Zeqiri, ² Markela Muca, ³ Arben Malko

^{1,2} Department of Applied Mathematics, Faculty of Natural Science, University of Tirana, Albania Tirana, Albania
amanda.zeqiri@fshn.edu.al
markela.muca@fshn.edu.al

³ Lev Tech, Software Development Company
arben1malko@gmail.com

Abstract— Processing types of data like noise, images and videos, which are raw data collected from technological or medical devices, is a challenge since numerical representation of them are very large datasets. Subtracting valuable information for surveillance, detection or biomedical purposes, consists in a pre-processing phase of the original dataset that includes reducing the number of variables without losing any important information or properties. Once the dimensionally reduction techniques are applied, more complex strategies and methods can be used to further process the data. Background subtraction techniques are necessary to separate moving objects from the steady ones, using a reference background frame.

This paper describes a collection of popular and effective methods used in image/video processing, particularly for background estimation. It highlights advantages, limitations, modifications and efficiency, starting from the standard approach (PCA) up to innovative methods using Krylov subspaces, associated with background estimation experiments.

Keywords— Principal components, Sparse PCA, Block Krylov subspace, SVD, Background subtraction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Real modern world problems generate huge amount of data every day. These raw data is very hard to manipulate or to get valuable information from. Data processing translates raw data into meaningful information by performing different techniques. Traditional approaches based on using the entire dataset become very impractical as the dimensions and number of variables increase therefore before applying different methods datasets are transformed into a suitable form by reducing dimension or the number of variables. Dimension reduction can be applied by keeping the most relevant variables only or by transforming the real dataset into a smaller dataset of new variables, that contain meaningful information and properties of the real dataset.

Dimensionally reduction can be very useful in many fields such as signal processing, image processing or video processing. Security and surveillance systems need image/video processing in order to detect, define or count people and other moving objects. To identify these elements background subtraction is applied i.e., separate the static elements called *background* from the other non-static elements referred to as *foreground*. Foreground do not have a significant contribution to the

background estimation as long as they are small and change position at different times.

One of the most widely used linear dimensionality reduction techniques, meaning each new variable being a linear combination of real variables, is Principal Component Analysis (PCA). This paper gives a detailed description of standard PCA (advantages and limitations), some modified versions (SPCA and Elastic net) and up to date Krylov subspace methods also used for dimensionality reduction and principal components approximation.

We conclude with background estimation experiments on different image datasets corresponding to three videos, to highlight differences between methods.

II. STANDARD PCA

Considering $X \in R^{n \times p}$ the real data matrix of dimensions n and p , where n rows represent the number of observations and the p columns represent the number of features/variables. The rows of matrix X are referred as $x_i = [x_{i1} \ x_{i2} \ \dots \ x_{ip}]$ than X can be written as $X = [x_1 \ x_2 \ \dots \ x_n]^T$.

Before processing the data, the columns of X are centered meaning from each column it is subtracted its sample mean $\bar{x}_j = \sum_{i=1}^n x_{ij} / n$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, p$. Sometimes it is necessary to scale the columns of X , that means to divide each variable by its sample variance, in order that each new variable has a sample variance of 1. This process is not always necessary, especially when the variables are all measured in the same units.

The main purpose of the dimensionally reduction techniques is to generate a $(n \times k)$ dimensional representation of the data $X_{n \times p}$, where k is much smaller than p , that would preserve the information present in the variables space. Linear PCA finds the best fit for this k -dimensional subspace by generating new variables as a linear combination of the original variables, such that the new variables capture maximal variance.

So, the new dimension-reduced data points are stored in the z_i rows of matrix $Z = YV^T \in R^{n \times p}$ and are called projected points. Matrix is $Y = XV \in R^{n \times k}$, where rows $x_i \in R^p$, for $i = 1, \dots, n$ of matrix $X_{n \times p}$, are transformed into rows $y_i \in R^k$, for $i = 1, \dots, n$ with less variables. Columns of $Y_{n \times k}$ are the k

principal component scores obtained by projecting X onto orthonormal vectors $v_j \in R^p$, for $j = 1, \dots, k$, which means they are orthogonal $v_i^T v_j = 0$ for $i \neq j$ and they are unit vectors $v^T v = 1$.

Vectors $v_1, v_2, \dots, v_k \in R^p$ are set as columns of matrix $V_{p \times k}$, they contain the loadings/directions/ coefficients of the k principal components and altogether explain the most variance in the data. Generally, the variance explained by the first k principal component directions should be at least 70%-80% of the total variance. The variance explained by principal component direction k is $d_k^2/n = \frac{1}{n} v_k^T (X^T X) v_k$, where $d_k = \sqrt{v_k^T (X^T X) v_k}$ and $S_n = \frac{1}{n} X^T X$ the sample covariance. So, in order to choose a suitable dimension, values close to one of function $\sum_{j=1}^k d_j^2 / \sum_{j=1}^p d_j^2$ mean the data can be explained by a small number of principal components. Sometimes the normalized scores of the principal components u_j are used. $u_j = (X v_j) / d_j \in R^n$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, k$ are also orthonormal vectors $u^T u = 1$.

One way of computing the first k principal component directions is by using Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) on the centered (standardized) data matrix $X_{n \times p}$. In contrast to Eigen-decomposition method which can only be applied to square matrices (sometimes does not exist even if the matrix is square), SVD exists for any type of rectangular matrices and does not need the calculation of $p \times p$ covariance or correlation matrix in order to evaluate the principal component directions v_j .

Matrix $X_{n \times p}$ can be decomposed as product of three matrices $X = U \cdot D \cdot V^T$ where $U_{n \times k}$ the matrix that contains as columns the normalized scores u_j , for for $j = 1, 2, \dots, k$; $D_{k \times k}$ a diagonal matrix $D = \text{diag}(d_1, d_2, \dots, d_k)$ with $d_1 \geq d_2 \geq \dots \geq d_k \geq 0$ and $V_{p \times k}$ the loadings matrix. The variance explained by principal component direction k is D_{kk}^2/n .

SVD provides simultaneously directions, scores and variances for the principal components [4]. $V_{p \times k}$ gives the eigenvectors of matrix $X^T X$ (right singular vectors of X) and $D_{k \times k}$ gives the square roots of the eigenvalues of matrix $X^T X$ (singular values of X), and hence the directions and standard deviations of the principal components for the data covariance matrix S_n . The principal component scores are $Y = UD$ and $U_{n \times k}$ has as columns the eigenvectors of matrix XX^T (scaled left singular vectors of X).

Standard PCA guarantees minimal loss of information during transformation since the principal components (PCs) sequentially capture the maximum variability among the columns of data matrix $X_{n \times p}$. Also, one single PC can be addressed without referring to the other PCs since PCs are not correlated.

On the other hand, in standard PCA each principal component is a linear combination of all variables, the loadings are typically non-zero which make it difficult to interpret the new

acquired information from the PCs and it is very sensitive to highly corrupted observations. Different techniques were proposed for sparse loadings/directions of the PCs and rotations techniques where the first to be applied as described by I.T Jolliffe [5]. Different thresholding techniques like Simple Thresholding, Diagonal Thresholding, Iterative Thresholding, Covariance Thresholding and Hard Thresholding can help to enhance the sparsity of the loadings/directions [6]. Another very interesting approach is to write PCA as a regression-type optimization problem.

Furthermore, in high-dimensional problems such as image processing and microarray information, where p is much greater than n , standard PCA has inconsistent results [7]. Computing all pairs of eigenvalues and corresponding eigenvectors (λ_i, v_i) for $i = 1, 2, \dots, p$ can be challenging. Estimating only the k most 'important' eigenpair can be achieved by projecting the original eigenvalue space onto a k -dimensional subspace which includes an invariant subspace associated with the 'important' eigenvectors. Krylov subspace methods as projection schemes can be used to generate these low-dimensional subspaces [8].

III. SPARSE PCA

This paper addresses different modified versions of PCA as a regularized regression problem with a weighted L_1 penalty term added to the traditional least-squares criterion, in order to get sparse PC directions. As addressed in SVD, standard PCA can be formulated as a least-squares problem, meaning, minimizing the sum of squared residual errors between the input data and the projected data:

$$\min_A \|X - XAA^T\|_F^2$$

subject to $A^T A = I$

The matrix of the right singular vectors V meets this least-squares criterion, hence $A = V$ has exactly the first k loadings of the standard PCA.

Now, considering the linear regression model $Y = \sum_{j=1}^p X_j \beta_j + \beta_0$ with n observations and p predictors. Let $Y = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n)^T$ be the measurement/response vector and $X_j = (x_{1j}, x_{2j}, \dots, x_{nj})^T$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, p$ the predictors, which are centered vectors. Let $X_{n \times p}$ be the matrix containing X_j as columns and β_j the regression coefficients vectors. The Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO) method imposes a constraint on the L_1 -norm of β_j as the sum of the absolute values of them. The Lasso sparse coefficients estimates are obtained by minimizing the Lasso criterion [9]:

$$\hat{\beta}_{lasso} = \arg \min_{\beta} \{ \|Y - \sum_{j=1}^p X_j \beta_j\|_2^2 + \lambda \sum_{j=1}^p |\beta_j| \}$$

where λ is a non-negative tuning/penalty parameter.

The lasso coefficients estimates shrink toward zero and depending on the nature of the L_1 penalty, some coefficients will be exactly equal to zero if λ is large enough. Lasso estimates make it easier to select variables but the number of variables selected are limited by n . In case where $p \gg n$, the LASSO

method can only select at most n features/variables when the number of observations is less than a thousand. In order to overcome this limitation of LASSO, H. Zou and T. Hastie [10] proposed the naïve elastic net model which is a regularized regression method that combines the Lasso penalty L_1 and ridge penalty L_2 . The sparse coefficients estimates are obtained by minimizing the naïve elastic net criterion:

$$\hat{\beta} = \arg \min_{\beta} \left\{ \|Y - \sum_{j=1}^p X_j \beta_j\|_2^2 + \lambda_2 \sum_{j=1}^p |\beta_j|^2 + \lambda_1 \sum_{j=1}^p |\beta_j| \right\}$$

where λ_1 and λ_2 are any non-negative tuning/penalty parameters. For $\lambda_1 = \lambda$ and $\lambda_2 = 0$ the lasso estimates $\hat{\beta}_{lasso}$ are obtained. Note that minimizing the naïve elastic net criterion is equivalent to a lasso-type optimization problem. For $\lambda_2 = \lambda$ and $\lambda_1 = 0$ the ridge estimates $\hat{\beta}_R$ are obtained by minimizing the ridge criterion:

$$\min_{\beta} \left\{ \|Y - \sum_{j=1}^p X_j \beta_j\|_2^2 + \lambda \sum_{j=1}^p |\beta_j|^2 \right\}$$

Penalty L_2 is not used to penalize the regression coefficients but it ensures the reconstruction of PCs. The approximations of the loading vectors \hat{V}_j of PCA equal normalized regression coefficients $\hat{\beta}_j / \|\hat{\beta}_j\|$ and $X\hat{V}_j$ are j -th approximated PC.

Viewing naïve elastic net as a regression-type optimization problem the function $(1 - \alpha) \sum_{j=1}^p |\beta_j| + \alpha \sum_{j=1}^p |\beta_j|^2$ is considered the elastic net penalty, where $\alpha = \lambda_2 / (\lambda_1 + \lambda_2)$ is a convex combination of the lasso penalty and the ridge penalty. For $0 < \alpha < 1$ the elastic net has the characteristics of both the ridge and lasso regression.

Since the naïve elastic net finds an estimator with a two-stage procedure which includes first finding $\hat{\beta}_R$ for each fixed λ_2 , and then apply a lasso type shrinkage, it faces over shrinkage. Over shrinkage does not help reduce the variances much and leads to poor predictions. To avoid this the coefficient estimates of the naïve elastic net are scaled by a scaling factor $(1 + \lambda_2)$, hence the elastic net coefficient estimates are $\hat{\beta}_{en} = (1 + \lambda_2) \cdot \hat{\beta}$ [10].

Elastic net is an automatic variable selection method and by choosing the tuning parameter $\lambda_2 > 0$ it overcomes the difficulty appearing in case where $p \gg n$. Elastic net can also select groups of correlated variables.

Sparse PCA based on [11] transforms the standard PCA problem to a regression-type problem and then uses Lasso or Elastic net to produce sparse coefficients/loadings by adding the Lasso penalty or the elastic net penalty into the least-squares criterion:

$$\min_{A,B} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n \|x_i - AB^T x_i\|_2^2 + \lambda \sum_{j=1}^k \|\beta_j\|_2^2 + \sum_{j=1}^k \lambda_{1,j} \|\beta_j\|_1 \right\}$$

subject to $A^T A = I_{k \times k}$

A general alternating algorithm is used to minimize this optimization problem [11] and in the case of image processing or microarray data, where $p \gg n$, the computational cost is very expensive since it requires a large number of nonzero loadings by solving each elastic net problem, for a positive finite λ . Another special case of the elastic net is when $\lambda \rightarrow \infty$ [10] and

it gives a convenient solution when $p \gg n$. This adapted algorithm is given below:

Step 1 Let A start at $V[; 1, 2, \dots, k]$, the loadings of the first k ordinary principal components.

Step 2 Given a fixed $A = [\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_k]$, solve the following elastic net problem by applying soft thresholding:

$$\hat{\beta}_j = \arg \min_{\beta_j} \left\{ -2\alpha_j^T (X^T X) \beta_j + \|\beta_j\|_F^2 + \lambda_{1,j} \|\beta_j\|_1 \right\}, \text{ for } j = 1, 2, \dots, k$$

which has the explicit form solution

$$\beta_j = \left(|\alpha_j^T X^T X| - \frac{\lambda_{1,j}}{2} \right)_+ \text{sgn}(|\alpha_j^T X^T X|) \text{ for } j = 1, 2, \dots, k.$$

Step 3 For a fixed $B = [\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_k]$, compute the SVD of $X^T X B = U D V^T$, then update $A = U V^T$.

Step 4 Repeat Steps 2–3, until convergence.

Step 5 Normalization: $\hat{V}_j = \frac{\beta_j}{\|\beta_j\|}$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, k$.

Some disadvantages of Sparse PCA are that it only approximates a single PC at a time and sometimes explains less variability in the data than standard PCA. The deflation process used after estimating each PC has consequences regarding loss of orthogonality and multiple tuning parameters. To pick good tuning parameters that give a good compromise between variance and sparsity several combinations of $\lambda_{1,j}$ are tested.

All the above methods for the sparse analysis can be found in R package *elasticnet* and Matlab package *SpaSM*. They can be downloaded respectively at the links:

<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/elasticnet/>
<https://www.jstatsoft.org/article/view/v084i10>.

IV. PRINCIPAL COMPONENT VIA LIMITED MEMORY KRYLOV SUBSPACE OPTIMIZATION

SVD decomposition was presented as a convenient tool for Standard PCA and to accelerate the performance of this method, a subspace optimization technique using limited memory block Krylov subspace was proposed by X. Liu [3]. This technique is based on the Simple Subspace Iteration (SSI), a generalization of the power method, and acceleration of SSI is achieved by reducing the number of iterations without having additional matrix-block multiplications of form $X^T X W$. Limited memory block Krylov accelerates the computation of the k -largest singular value decomposition of matrix $X_{n \times p}$, also the k -largest eigenvalues and leading eigenvectors of matrix $X^T X$ which maximize the Rayleigh-Ritz criterion:

$$\max_W \|XW\|_F^2$$

subject to $W^T W = 1, W \in R^{p \times k}$

First, we apply the usual SSI, starting from an initial point $W^{(0)}$ and compute the next iterate $X^{(i+1)} \in \text{orth}(X^T X W^{(i)})$. To reduce the number of iterations in the process, the last iterate

$W^{(i)}$ is updated by an intermediate iterate $\widehat{W}^{(i)}$ and the next iterate is computed as $X^{(i+1)} \in \text{orth}(X^T X \widehat{W}^{(i)})$. The subspace optimization problem is the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{W}^{(i)} &= \arg \min_W \|XW\|_F^2 \\ \text{subject to } W^T W &= I, W \in \mathcal{S}^{(i)} \end{aligned}$$

for a chosen subspace $\mathcal{S}^{(i)}$ with a block Krylov subspace structure. $\mathcal{S}^{(i)}$ is the subspace spanned by the current i -th iterate and the previous s iterates: $\mathcal{S}^{(i)} := \text{span}\{W^{(i)}, W^{(i-1)}, \dots, W^{(i-s)}\}$ with block size $s \geq 0$. The block size is very important for this technique and usually at each iteration it is set a value s_{max} . The greater the value of s_{max} , the smaller the number of iterations. On the other hand, by increasing s_{max} the computational costs per iteration also increases. Different experiments indicate that 2, 3 and 4 are good suitable values for the block size/memory length but there are also other strategies adapted for selection (see, [3]).

The current and s iterate blocks obtained are placed into matrix $W = W_s^{(i)} \in R^{p \times q}$ where $q = k \cdot (1 + s)$ is the number of columns in $W_s^{(i)}$. SSI simultaneously computes blocks $XW_s^{(i)}$ and they are as placed in matrix $Y = Y_s^{(i)} \in R^{n \times q}$. Note the difference between collection matrix (bold) and its blocks. Matrix $W \in \mathcal{S}^{(i)}$ if and only if $W = WV$ for some $V \in R^{q \times k}$, so the subspace optimization problem is transformed into the generalized eigenvalue decomposition problem:

$$\begin{aligned} \max_V \|(XW)V\|_F^2 \\ \text{subject to } V^T(W^T W)V = I \end{aligned}$$

The last problem is transformed into an equivalent and more specific decomposition problem since matrix $W^T W$ can become numerically rank deficient:

$$\begin{aligned} \max_V \|\mathbf{R}V\|_F^2 \\ \text{subject to } V^T V = I \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathbf{R} = R_s^{(i)} := XQ_s^{(i)}$ and $\mathbf{Q} = Q_s^{(i)} \in \text{orth}(W_s^{(i)})$ an orthonormal basis for $\mathcal{S}^{(i)}$ such that matrix $W \in \mathcal{S}^{(i)}$ is expressed as $W = \mathbf{Q}V$ for some $V \in R^{q \times k}$.

To compute \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{R} even when the matrix W is numerically rank deficient it is used the following procedure. The last block $W^{(i)}$ is kept intact and the rest of the blocks are projected onto the null space of $W^{(i)T}$. This way matrix $\mathbf{P}_W = P_W^{(i)} := (I - W^{(i)}(W^{(i)T})^T)[W^{(i-1)}, W^{(i-2)}, \dots, W^{(i-s)}]$ is obtained with dimensions $p \times (k \cdot s)$. Next, stabilization is performed by deleting the columns of \mathbf{P}_W whose Euclidean norms are below a threshold $\varepsilon_1 > 0$.

Also, the same columns deleted for \mathbf{P}_W are deleted for matrix $\mathbf{P}_Y = P_Y^{(i)} := [Y^{(i-1)}, \dots, Y^{(i-s)}] - Y^{(i)}(W^{(i)T})^T[W^{(i-1)}, W^{(i-2)}, \dots, W^{(i-s)}]$. Computing the eigenvalue decomposition of the Gram matrix for \mathbf{P}_W :

$$\mathbf{P}_W^T \mathbf{P}_W = U_W \Lambda_W U_W^T \in R^{(k \cdot s) \times (k \cdot s)}$$

orthogonal matrix U_W and diagonal matrix Λ_W are obtained. Afterwards, a stabilization step is performed by deleting the eigenvalues in Λ_W , and corresponding columns in U_W , that are less than $\varepsilon_2 > 0$ in order to shrink them. To generate matrix \mathbf{R} first we need to stably construct matrix \mathbf{Q} as $\mathbf{Q} = Q_s^{(i)} := [W^{(i)}, \mathbf{P}_W U_W \Lambda_W^{-1/2}]$. Now that \mathbf{R} is available we can compute the k leading eigenvectors of matrix $\mathbf{R}^T \mathbf{R} \in R^{q \times q}$, a small symmetric positive definite matrix. Let \widehat{V} be the solution to the generalized eigenvalue decomposition problem $\max_V \|\mathbf{R}V\|_F^2$ s.t. $V^T V = I$, then $\widehat{W}^{(i)} = \mathbf{Q}\widehat{V}$ and $\widehat{Y}^{(i)} = \mathbf{R}\widehat{V}$. To conclude, the next iterate of SSI is $W^{(i+1)} \in \text{orth}(X^T \widehat{Y}^{(i)})$ and $Y^{(i+1)} = XW^{(i+1)}$.

This algorithm is called the LMSVD algorithm and it is available as a Matlab directory at the the following link: <https://www.caam.rice.edu/~yzhang/LMSVD/lmsvd.html#download>.

V. KRYLOV PCA

This method is used to estimate the dimension of the principal/dominant subspace of the covariance matrix and approximate this dominant subspace at the same time by using Krylov subspace-based methods. As pointed out in the previews section Block Krylov methods are very useful and give optimal PCs for different types of high dimensional data matrices $X_{n \times p}$. These methods have the advantage to avoid forming the sample covariance matrix $S_n = \frac{1}{n} X^T X$ and computation of its full eigenvalue decomposition. In order to compute the top k eigenvalues of S_n and corresponding eigenvectors, the Block Lanczos algorithm can be used [2].

The criterion proposed by Sh. Ubaru [1] for selecting an appropriate dimension q of dominant subspace is derived using random matrix perturbation theory results and also contains a penalty parameter:

$$q = \arg \min_k \left\{ \frac{n}{2\sigma^2} \sum_{i=k+1}^p (\lambda_i - \sigma)^2 - C_n \frac{(p-k)(p-k-1)}{2} \right\}$$

where λ_i for $i = 1, 2, \dots, p$ are the eigenvalues of S_n , σ the noise variance related to the remaining $(p - k)$ non dominant eigenvalues and penalty C_n . Different methods can be used to estimate σ such as the thresholding method in image processing and techniques for approximating spectral densities of the matrix.

The penalty parameter has the following bound $C_n > \frac{(p+2\sqrt{np})^2}{n(p-q-1)}$.

Approximations θ_i and y_i (for $i = 1:k$) of the k dominant eigenvalues and corresponding eigenvectors (loadings) of S_n are obtained by using m steps of the Block Krylov Subspace $\mathbb{K}^{(m)}$. We recall that the m -th Block Krylov Subspace is $\mathbb{K}^{(m)}(A, V) = \text{span}\{V, AV, \dots, A^{m-1}V\}$ for a symmetric matrix A and $V \in R^{p \times k}$ a random matrix such that $V \not\subseteq \text{null}(A)$. For a

given error ϵ the number of optimal Block Krylov steps is $m = \log(p) / \sqrt{\epsilon}$. The error ϵ is related to the spectral gap of S_n (or singular gap of $X_{n \times p}$) so it can be equal to $(\lambda_k / \lambda_{k+1}) - 1$ and selected as the threshold. The detailed algorithm explaining this process is called Krylov PCA and it is the following (Sh. Ubaru et al., 2018):

Inputs: Transpose data matrix $X_{p \times n}$, noise σ , penalty C_n and tolerance ϵ

Step 1 Set $IC = \text{zeros}(p, 1)$, $Q = []$, $k = 1$ and $m = \log(p) / \sqrt{\epsilon}$

Step 2 Compute norm $\phi = \frac{1}{n^2} \|X\|_F^4 - \frac{2\sigma}{n} \|X\|_F^2 + p\sigma^2$

For $k = 1, 2, \dots, p$ do

Step 3 Generate a random vector v_k with $\|v_k\|_2 = 1$.

Step 4 $K = \frac{1}{n} [Xv_k, (XX^T)Xv_k, \dots, (XX^T)^{m-1}Xv_k]$

Step 5 $Q = \text{orth}([Q, K])$, $Q = Q(:, 1:k)$.

Step 6 $T = \frac{1}{n} Q^T XX^T Q$.

Step 7 Compute eigen decomposition: $[V, \theta] = \text{eig}(T)$.

Step 8 $IC(k) = n(\phi - \sum_{i=1}^k (\theta_i - \sigma)^2) - C_n \frac{(p-k)(p-k-1)}{2}$

Step 9 If $(k > 1)$ && $IC(k) > IC(k - 1)$ then
break;
end if

End For

Output: Estimated dimension $q = k - 1$ and $Y = QV$ containing the approximated loadings as columns.

Steps 4 to 7 can be replaced by a modified version of the regular Lanczos algorithm [8], which builds an orthonormal basis for the Krylov subspace using only matrix-vector multiplications and updates the previous subspace Q and the tridiagonal matrix T . For the experiments used on image and video processing in this paper, Krylov PCA was implemented in Matlab Software function $[q, Y, \lambda] = \text{Krylov_PCA}(X, \sigma, \epsilon, \text{penalty}, \text{maxit})$.

VI. BACKGROUND ESTIMATION

In PCA analysis the principal components of a video are the elements of the matrix representation of n frames of size $a \times b$

that remain relatively constant over n frames i.e., background components. This means removing non static elements i.e., foreground, which can be seen as a noise added to the ground truth (GT) background. GT can be selected from one or a group of frames from the video without moving objects. The video database for experiments is SBI dataset available at <https://sbmi2015.na.icar.cnr.it/SBIdataset.html>. Three image sequences of different scenarios (less or more activity) have been selected to use the above methods for background estimation and compare them to the corresponding GTs. General information about selected datasets is presented in Table I.

TABLE I. DATASET GENERAL INFORMATION.

Dataset	Resolution	n	p
CaVignal	136x200	258	27200
Foliage	144x200	394	28800
HighwayII	240x320	500	76800

At first, each selected frame (image) of a dataset is transformed from three dimensional arrays $a \times b \times c$ for $c = 1, 2, 3$ (corresponding to RGB color channels) into three 2-dimensional arrays $a \times b$, for a constant c . Then the elements of each two-dimensional array are rearranged as row vectors of length $p = a \times b$. For each dataset, using n frames from the sequence, are consequently formed three $n \times p$ data matrices. All three matrices corresponding to the sequence are centered (standardized) before using Krylov PCA and other methods include these options as arguments of the algorithms used in R or Matlab packages.

After getting PCs approximation Y_i for $i = 1:3$ and store projected points in matrices Z_i for $i = 1:3$ for each sequence, the projected data go through de-standardization since the input matrices were standardized. As a final step, we reconstruct the estimated image back to 3D. Background images estimated from SPCA, LMSVD and Krylov PCA method are listed below beside their GTs.

Figure 1. CaVignal Dataset

Figure 2. Foliage Dataset

Figure 3. HighwayII Dataset

In the first video CaVignal the foreground object is just one (a man), that appears in the same location in more than half of the frames used and then moves slowly through the frames. Even though there is only one object, the persistent presence affects the background subtraction, so the object significantly appears in all estimations (Fig. 1). The second video (Foliage) has more foreground objects (leaves) that obstruct the background but are not as firm during the sequence as the object in CaVignal video. All three methods in this case give a satisfactory result in background estimation (Fig. 2). Whereas the last video sequence (HighwayII) as expected, gives a very good estimation (Fig. 3). Although there is a lot of activity (moving cars), foreground objects change locations very quickly and the background is exposed most of the time.

In order to compare GTs and background images obtained from each method, peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR) is shown in Table II.

TABLE II. PSNR FOR EACH METHOD OF ALL DATASETS.

Method	SPCA	LMSVD	Krylov PCA
Data			
CaVignal	20.01	23.64	20.24
Foliage	12.26	28.05	12.26
HighwayII	32.45	33.18	32.39

As seen in the pictures and Table II, LMSVD prevails over other methods for background estimating regardless of the activity in datasets. Meanwhile, SPCA and Krylov PCA have close accuracy to one another. When foreground objects continually move and the background is very exposed SPCA gives better estimations than Krylov PCA. Note that in this case (HighwayII) all methods give higher PSNR compared to other datasets. When foreground objects are more persistent but do not obstruct most of the background Krylov PCA gives better results than SPCA. In case where most of the background is not exposed during the sequence SPCA and Krylov PCA make no difference.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

Although Standard PCA is a great tool for PCs estimation, when it comes to high-dimensional applications such as image processing where $p \gg n$, it has inconsistent results. Also, when increasing the number of variables p , Standard PCA makes it difficult to name and interpret the new groups of variables. Different sparse PCA techniques have been used to resolve deficiencies of the standard approach. SPCA introduced by H. Zou [11] shows optimal results (a modified version of LASSO and Elastic Net) and only a few slightly-modified algorithms have been proposed using the same approach. On the other hand, these sparse techniques depend on multiple sparsity penalties/parameters which require other methods to be evaluated or different experimental tests for selection. Krylov subspace-based methods (including Block Krylov subspace) like LMSVD and Krylov PCA are contemporary methods and of high interest in data processing. Background estimation using Krylov subspace methods is very convenient due to low memory cost and their efficiency in case of high number of foreground elements (noise).

REFERENCES

- [1] Sh. Ubaru, A. Seghouane and Y. Saad, "Find the dimension that counts: Fast dimension estimation and Krylov PCA", *arXiv, Cornell University*, 2018.
- [2] C. Musco and C. Musco, "Randomized Block Krylov Methods for Stronger and Faster Approximate Singular Value Decomposition", *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 2015.
- [3] X. Liu, Z. Wen, and Y. Zhang, "Limited Memory Block Krylov Subspace Optimization for Computing Dominant Singular Value Decomposition," *SIAM Journal on Scientific Computing*, 2013.
- [4] I.T. Jolliffe, *Principal Component Analysis, Second Edition*, Springer, USA, 2002.
- [5] I.T. Jolliffe, "Rotation of principal components: choice of normalization constraints", *Journal of Applied Statistics*, 1995.
- [6] M. Sezgin and B. Sankur, "Survey over image thresholding techniques and quantitative performance evaluation", *Journal of Electronic Imaging*, 2004.
- [7] M. Johnstone and A.Y. Lu, "On Consistency and Sparsity for Principal Components Analysis in High Dimensions", *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 2009.
- [8] Y. Saad, *Iterative Methods for Sparse Linear Systems, Second Edition*, Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics, 2003.
- [9] R. Tibshirani, "Regression Shrinkage and Selection via the Lasso," *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society*, 1996.
- [10] H. Zou and T. Hastie, "Regularization and variable selection via the elastic net", *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series B*, 2005.
- [11] H. Zou, T. Hastie and R. Tibshirani "Sparse Principal Component Analysis", *Journal of Computational and Graphical Statistics*, 2006.